

Principles and Methods of Organizing Production Processes

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Annotation:

Planning is the process by which an organization makes management decisions and solutions about the choice of goals, what needs to be done to achieve them. The enterprise is able to create a rational model by consciously setting a goal for itself and take into account objective conditions in it.

Keywords: mathematical modeling, planning, organization, goal, achievement, management decision, solutions.

Introduction The purpose of the enterprise is to achieve a previously thought-out, ultimately, result based on its activities. The intention of the enterprise, which is considered a production team, is made on the basis of establishing objective laws and prospects for its development.

Here it requires the selection of optimal decisions with minimal costs and losses to achieve and implement a certain goal. For this, economic mathematical methods and Ehms are used in the development of managerial decisions. The organization plans all its actions on the way to achieving its goals, which means that it remains one of the important elements of management (unsur). Planning is the process by which an organization makes management decisions and solutions about the choice of goals, what needs to be done to achieve them. The enterprise is able to create a rational model by consciously setting a goal for itself and take into account objective conditions in it. Enterprises perform certain tasks in order to achieve their goals.

It is the work of the team's activities aimed at achieving the resulting indicators. Each unit has its own goals and objectives. The task can be described as the final results in the execution of the production program. The purpose of the enterprise - calculated qualitative and quantitative indicators of its activities.

The qualitative indicators of the goal are as follows:

Improving the organizational structure of production management for automation of management specialists, economists, accountants, workplaces;

Sex, implementation of the retraining of personnel of the enterprise;

Organization of a qualified personnel apparatus in the management apparatus to improve the efficiency of management and production;

Elimination of production time loss of workers and servants.

The function of each production unit can be different. But their goal will be the same: to fulfill the program of production of products, in which money consists in achieving the minimum costs of funds, time, labor, materials.

In the management process, it is necessary to ensure the compliance and subordination of current goals to prospective goals, Private goals to general goals, intermediate goals to final goals. More attention should be paid to the implementation of the main goals. Management activities of an enterprise or equivalent business entities should be aimed at performing these tasks in full.

The ability to distinguish the main goal from secondary tasks is one of the most important professional indicators of modern managers. The management process will be mainly periodic (cyclic) in nature. It begins with setting goals and objectives, and ends with completing them, that is, achieving certain results.

Based on the information received about the results (the level of achievement of the goal), new tasks are set, and the management cycle begins again. The number of such cycles is several, which are represented in the first place by the peculiarities of the control object and other indicators. In practice, for various reasons, production may deviate from the specified dimensions, while management may not achieve the set goal. In such cases, deviations are removed by operative regulation and the normative functioning of the production process is ensured.

Research methodology the efficiency of enterprise management, the less time spent on the formation and implementation of goals, the higher. This is achieved due, in addition to the experience and qualifications of the head (manager) of the enterprise and other persons responsible for performing management tasks, the use of a set of organizational and technical measures to reduce the time spent on management practice and work routine, mechanize and automate management processes, and rationally organize the adoption and implementation of management decisions. Management activities at the enterprise are also carried out on the basis of certain principles.

These principles, firstly, establish agreements between the participants in production, and secondly, prevent possible errors and increase the effectiveness of managerial labor.

The activities of industrial enterprises consist in the performance of the following tasks based on the current conditions:

Production and delivery of high-quality products in accordance with the growing requirements of consumers;

Growing labor productivity in a continuous way;

The unspoken fulfillment in time of the planned tasks of the enterprise for the production and sale of products of each enterprise;

More productive use of basic production funds;

It consists in improving the use of working capital.

In the production process, inter-sex production relations and management relations are established, which directly indicate the joint Organization of the activities of producers, management personnel and production participants. The final results and goals of the enterprise management, the organization of the lines of formation of production and the management process determine the requirements for the organizational structure.

Methods and functions of the organizational structure of management are used to carry out the above actions, relationships. Management functions determine the characteristics of people in the process of production, characterizing Labor analysis, specialization in the management environment (field).

Among the functions, the planning function of management takes its place, ensuring that a certain object, a certain goal, is achieved. The planning function indicates the development of a production program at different periods of the plan and the identification of specific tasks for each unit. In the formation of a production program, it is necessary to know the value, conveyance, distribution and rational use of the resources contained in it, and the function of planning will be of important economic importance.

But, a good plan is not enough to achieve any goal. It is necessary to justify the drawn up plan, prove its correctness. Prediction plays an important role in this. It can be seen that planning is a complex process, which can consist of the following components: specific goals, issues to be solved in order to achieve them, requirements for the resources that will be needed to solve issues, methods of solving issues, planning where the processes will be carried out. Planning work begins with the formation of the main task of the organization, and in this, the specialist is exposed to such factors as materials, labor resources and funds providers, laws and state governing bodies, consumers and competitors, technology, the state of the economy, political situation and social, cultural, spirituality. For an organization, a procedure is developed for solving such issues as how to choose goals, what decisions or solutions to achieve them, allocation of resources, adaptation to the environment, coordination of internal interactions. The organization should also provide for the delivery of the product to the consumer again, making purchases, depending on the scope of planning. The change in the volume of all manufactured products will also affect the volume of the system in the planning of the next product cycle.

The production plan affects the value of all types of production costs: storage, product size, stay without cancellation. The essence of planning is a deep, comprehensively developed complex plan, the implementation of the main task (mission)of the organization and the implementation of its goals.

The organization of the developed plan is an important stage. The organization of the internal economy of the organization, such as maintaining management positions, determining the interaction between leaders and subordinates, as well as the distribution of issues to be solved within the framework of the organization, is assigned to the employees of the Operational Department.

Conclusion In the process of organizing relations, issues, powers are transferred (distributed) from above to below. In this case, it will be necessary to attach special importance to the overlap of issue and authority. The failure of each issue to be provided with appropriate regulatory authority (the limited right to use resources within the organization) leads to the exploitation of resources and, accordingly, the failure to perform work.

Literature used

1. Philip T.Kotler, Kevin Lane Keller. Marketing Management.– 15-th edition, Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Pearson Education, 2016

2. Fred R. David Francis Marion Strategic Management concepts and cases thirteenth edition University Florence, South Carolina, 2016 page 256
3. Rodionova O.L., Shashnikova N.K. Production and production management. Tomsk Polytechnic University Publishing House 2008.